

DISTRIBUTED FIELD NETWORK OF WIRELESS SENSORS FOR GROUNDWATER MONITORING

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Annotation: The article describes the wireless installation of groundwater monitoring networks, data exchange, acceleration of software application processes, the type and topology of the network, its components. At the same time, the issues of the wireless field network protocol, topology and topology of the hybrid network necessary for the effective operation of the geoinformation system for monitoring groundwater based on remote sensing were considered. The structure of the architecture of the field mobile sensor network is presented.

Keywords: network, protocol, topology, hybrid network, algorithm, monitoring, groundwater, remote sensing, hydrogeology.

When designing a data collection and management system for remote sensing and Earth monitoring, developers need to choose not only sensors, control devices and controllers, but also the type and topology of the network, while taking into account the following three components:

- network - transport component;
- component connecting network nodes;
- protocol component.

Field equipment for hydrogeological monitoring includes sensors, transducers, switches, valves, motors and actuators. In a typical system, all of these devices are assembled separately, often by different engineers. Mechanical engineers are typically responsible for valves, motors, and actuators, while control engineers work with transducers, sensors, and transmitters. Because each field device was connected directly to another device, such as a controller or HMI system, this approach was not a problem. In the last decade of network-centric development, they are simply devices connected to switches, controllers, HMI systems, and many other "network nodes".

In wireless sensor networks, sensors and other field devices equipped with microprocessors become intelligent networks and can communicate with host computers and directly with other field devices via digital data. The widespread

use of such devices in the automation of the field of hydrogeology increases the possibilities of their interconnection with controllers and other devices.

Various types of media can be used to work on the network. In this case, the physical topology of the network is represented by the configuration of cable connections. From coaxial cables, stranded twisted pairs to fiber optic cables, the choice of transmission medium determines the size, range and maximum network capacity. Since the early 2000s, low-power RF channels such as Wi-Fi and 802.15.4 have been added to existing data transmission media. The logical topology of the network shows the way signals interact without taking into account the physical connection of network devices and nodes. The logical topology of the network is mainly determined by the network protocols used:

Wireless field network protocols. In field networks other than the Ethernet network standard, Modbus RTU can be implemented via a multipoint RS-485 interface, as well as on the basis of various standards, ending with HART, Profibus, Foundation fieldbus and wireless personal Network (WPAN) standard. Wired and wireless networks differ in their transmission medium and use the same network topologies, so they interact and work together in complex configurations.

Field wireless networks are used in the same way as wired networks, based on different protocols. There are at least five common standardized wireless network protocols: Zigbee, IEC 62591-WirelessHART, ISA100.11a and the Chinese WIA-PA protocol. All of them will be based on IEEE 802.15.4, a low—power wireless data transmission standard for networks.

1 picture. Hybrid network topology

Topology of a field wireless network. In the field of hydrogeology, it is often advisable to use the following network topologies: such network protocols as linear, ring, cellular, star, tree, bus are effective. We need to create a network topology to solve the problems of groundwater monitoring based on remote sensing of the earth. We use hybrid network topologies for efficient data exchange. Networks with different topologies can be chained if all nodes use the same protocol. Thus, it is possible to build a network based on several protocols that allow data exchange over wired and wireless connections within a single enterprise or factory. For this reason, hybrid network topologies are becoming a common solution. For enterprises in the field of hydrogeology, it can use a Profibus wired network, which, in turn, connects to a wireless network gateway and an Ethernet-based Modbus TCP/IP network.

Sensor nodes of sensor networks consist of one or more sensors, a microcontroller, external memory, a radio transmitter, an analog-to-digital converter, an antenna and a battery. In this case, the nodes are limited in memory, battery power, computing and radio power due to their small size. However, the architecture of the mobile sensor node is almost the same as that of a traditional sensor node. Mobile sensor nodes should be equipped with additional devices, such as localizers, mobilizers and electric generators. The architecture of the mobile sensor node will look like this:

2 picture. Mobile field sensor network architecture

In this case, the location unit is used to determine the position of the sensor node, and the mobilizer ensures the mobility of the sensor node. The power generator unit is designed to generate energy to meet the further energy needs of the sensor node using some method such as a solar battery.

Network topology plays an important role in MSN for mobile sensor nodes when transmitting data to the receiver/base station. Then the recipient and the remote user server are connected via the Internet. The performance of large-scale mobile wireless sensor networks depends only on the data acquisition scheme or topology management. Thus, the topology provides a guaranteed reliable network and the best quality of service in terms of mobility, traffic, connectivity, etc. With such considerations, efficient data collection with low power consumption can be achieved in the network topology.

LEACH is one of the most popular algorithms for dynamic clustering of sensor networks based on hierarchical routing, fully developed for distributed environments and does not require knowledge of the global network. The sensor node uses the received signal power as well as threshold values to select the cluster head forming the cluster. Here, the rounding or updating topology interval for data transmission is divided into fixed intervals of equal length. Each sensor node in the network has an equal chance to act as the head of the cluster by choosing a random number from 0 to 1, so the sensor nodes can slow down.

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